

COMPARATIVE ASSESSMENT OF THE EFFECTS OF DIFFERENT TYPES OF RETRACTION ON PERIODONTAL TISSUES

Iroda Erkinovna Khojaeva¹

Alieva Nazokat Muratjanovna²

Akhmedov Murod Rakhmonberdiyevich³

¹⁻²⁻³Tashkent State Dental Institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6748784>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 28th May 2022

Accepted: 02nd June 2022

Online: 05th June 2022

KEY WORDS

retraction floss, retraction
paste, gingival sulcus

ABSTRACT

The traumatic effects of the retraction procedure only occur when the marginal gingival structure is not taken into consideration and retraction agents are not individually selected. Consequently, any manipulation of the marginal gingiva during prosthodontics must be performed with the utmost care to avoid an unpredictable marginal periodontal reaction. The problem of marginal gingiva protection is very topical. The influence of the retraction procedure on the marginal periodontal tissues with different gingival biotypes, the effect of hemostatic agents and the design of retraction sutures remain insufficiently studied.

Introduction. In orthopedic dentistry there are two main requirements for working impressions during the fabrication of fixed dentures: high dimensional accuracy and high quality display of the preparation boundaries. The contouring of the gingival margin is extremely important for the long-term clinical success of the treatment. Lack of marginal contouring can lead to inflammation of periodontal tissues and an increased risk of tooth decay. Preventing marginal periodontitis and gingival recession after the preparation of retraction manipulations is very important in the practice of dentistry. Preparation boundaries should be placed above the gingival sulcus, but in certain cases it is necessary to place the boundary below the gingiva. The most common methods of gingival preparation are mechanical and mechanical-chemical methods, using only retraction floss or floss with the addition of

a bleeding solution. While considerable progress has been made in terms of the hydrophilicity of impression materials and their ability to reproduce detail, making an accurate impression is still a matter of debate, especially when the preparation line is below the gingiva. The right choice of retraction technique can improve the quality of the impression and its clinical performance as well as reduce time costs.

Study objective: evaluation and comparison of the gingival condition after the use of three different retraction systems.

Materials and methods: 30 people aged 20 to 25 years were examined. Prerequisites for patient inclusion were absence of active inflammation of periodontal tissues, sulcus probing depth not more than 3 mm and absence of bleeding during probing. The study included preparation for metaloceramic and ceramic restorations.

The edges were positioned 1-2 mm below the gingiva. For retraction, UltraPak 00 non-impregnated retraction floss; Gingi-Pak00 epinephrine retraction floss; Traxodent Hemodent Paste Retraction System retraction floss were used. Ultrapak, Sure Cord - retraction sutures are made of 100% cotton that is tied into a chain of thousands of tiny loops. The thread is available in sizes from 000 to 3. Gingi-Pak retraction sutures are also made of 100% cotton, available in sizes from 00 to 3. The thread is impregnated with epinephrine, which has a significant effect on the periodontal tissues, so it is not recommended to perform retraction with this thread if you have periodontal disease. Traxodent retraction paste is a soft, absorbent, fast-acting paste. The soft paste applies gentle pressure on the gingival sulcus and absorbs excess gingival fluid. Aluminum chloride has an astringent effect. Unimpregnated Ultrapak 00 retraction sutures were looped tightly and placed in the gingival sulcus and left there for 10 minutes. During gingival retraction with Gingi-Pak sized 00 sutures, factory-impregnated with epinephrine, were placed in the gingival sulcus and left in place for 5 minutes. Traxodent Hemodent Paste Retraction System was used according to the manufacturer's instructions. Impressions were taken after the retraction stage. The clinical effectiveness of the retraction sutures was evaluated according to the following criteria: Time taken for the procedure (acceptable (+), prolonged (-)) Ease of method (Easy (+): introduction of the thread and/or cap into the sulcus once and without displacement; Difficult (-): Placing the thread and/or cap in the sulcus more than once and/or appearance of

displacement of the thread or cap from the sulcus) Bleeding after retraction (yes (+), no(-)) Quality of the impression at the gingival margin (unacceptable (-),very good(+)) Deterioration of general well-being of the patient: yes (+), no (-) (short-term increase in heart rate up to 95 beats per minute, increase in blood pressure by 20% from the initial one, headaches, anxiety) Research results: The term retraction (Latin: Retractio) literally means pulling away, reduction, wrinkling. Orthopedists understand this word to mean the pharmacomechanical enlargement of the gingival sulcus in order to introduce impression material into the gaping cavity to accurately represent the ledge, the neck of the tooth and the bottom of the sulcus. In this study, unimpregnated threads (Ultrapak), epinephrine-impregnated threads (GINGI-PAK) and retraction paste (Traxodent Hemodent Paste Retraction System) were considered. The results of the study are presented in the table. 1. Time taken for the procedure 2.Ease of the method 3.Bleeding after retraction 4.Quality of the impression in the gingival margin area 5. Deterioration of general well-being of the patient UltraPak - + + - - Gingi-Pak - - - - + + Traxodent + - + - When analyzing the results, it was found that the retraction floss without impregnation allows a slight pushing back of the marginal gingiva, which can be complicated by improper trimming of the plaster stamper and inaccurate fit of the crown to the natural stump of the tooth. In addition, the placement of the floss into the periodontal sulcus caused unpleasant or painful sensations for the patient. Also, retraction floss without hemostatic fluid proved to be the least effective in terms of impression quality, as the local tissues

regained their volume immediately after removal of the floss. Another disadvantage of the thread was bleeding after its removal, which complicates the work of the dentist. The only, but not insignificant, advantage of this thread is that it can be used in people with existing somatic pathologies, as it does not affect the general condition of the patient. Good gingival retraction rates were observed with the Gingi-Pac sutures with epinephrine, which provided high quality impressions. However, there were serious drawbacks: even in the absence of somatic pathology, there was a worsening of the patient's general well-being, expressed as a short-term increase in heart rate up to 95 beats per minute, an increase in blood pressure by 20% of the initial one, headaches, anxiety. It was also found that GINGI-PAK floss is more difficult to fit into the dental sulcus than Ultrapac, significantly affects the periodontal tissues, has a prolonged vasoconstriction and prevents bleeding after removal of the floss. Traxodent paste had the best

performance. The retraction technique was the easiest and fastest. The marginal gingiva was sufficiently retracted, which contributed to good impression quality. There was no bleeding after the cap and paste were removed. There was also no deterioration in the patient's general well-being.

Conclusions: The study found that the Traxodent Hemodent Paste Retraction System ranked first in all evaluation criteria. It does not cause bleeding or general well-being, is easy to apply, and has the best impression quality scores. In second place was Gingi-Pak00, an epinephrine-impregnated retraction suture. Its main disadvantage is its impact on the general well-being of the patient. The UltraPak 00 retraction thread without hemostatic fluid was the least effective in terms of impression quality, as the local tissues regained their volume immediately after removal of the thread. There was also bleeding after the removal of the thread, which made the doctor's work more difficult.

References:

1. Eroshkina E. A. // Influence of gingival retraction method on the depth of penetration of corrective material into dental sulcus during impression taking // Scientific proceedings of X international congress "Health and education in the XXI century". "Innovative technologies in biology and medicine". 2009. C. 1069-1070.
2. Mikeeva I. M. // Method of working field isolation in dentistry. // MED-press-inform, 2007. C 25-30.
3. Akhme Dov Alisher Astanovich, Rizayev Jasur Alimdjanovich, Sadikov Abdushukur Abdujamilevich, Turayev Alimjan Bakhriddnovich. (2021). The State of Periodontal Tissues in Athletes Engaged in Cyclic Sports. *Annals of the Romanian Society for Cell Biology*, 235–241. Retrieved from <https://www.annalsofrscb.ro/index.php/journal/article/view/102>
3. Djuraev, A. M., & Khalimov, R. J. (2020). New methods for surgical treatment of perthes disease in children. *International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation*, 24(2), 301-307.
4. Dzhuraev, A., Usmanov, Sh., Rakhmatullaev, H., & Khalimov, R. (2021). Our experience with surgical treatment of congenital elevation of the scapula in young children. *Medicine and Innovations*, 1(4), 37-44.

5. Khodjieva D.T., Pulatov S.S., Khaidarova D.K. All about hemorrhagic stroke in elderly and senile persons (own observations) // Science of Young People (Eruditio Juvenium). 2015. №3. C. 87-96.
6. Ismoilov, O. I., Murodkosimov, S. M., Kamalova, M. I., Turaev, A. Y., & Mahmudova, S. K. (2021). The Spread Of SARS-Cov-2 Coronavirus In Uzbekistan And Current Response Measures. The American Journal of Medical Sciences and Pharmaceutical Research, 3(03), 45-50.
7. Khamdamov B.Z. Indicators of immunocytocine status in purulent-necrotic lesions of the lower extremities in patients with diabetes mellitus.//American Journal of Medicine and Medical Sciences, 2020 10(7) 473-478 DOI: 10.5923/j.ajmm.2020.- 1007.08
8. M. I. Kamalova, N.K.Khaidarov, Sh.E.Islamov, Pathomorphological Features of hemorrhagic brain strokes, Journal of Biomedicine and Practice 2020, Special issue, pp. 101-105
9. Khodjieva D. T., Khaydarova D. K., Khaydarov N. K. Complex evaluation of clinical and instrumental data for justification of optimal treatment activities in patients with resistant forms of epilepsy. American Journal of Research. USA. № 11-12, 2018. C.186-193.
10. Khodjieva D. T., Khaydarova D. K. Clinical and neurophysiological characteristics of post-insular cognitive disorders and issues of therapy optimization. Central Asian Journal of Pediatrics. Dec.2019. P 82-86
11. Sadridin Sayfullaevich Pulatov. (2022). Efficacy of ipidacrine in the recovery period of ischaemic stroke. World Bulletin of Public Health, 7, 28-32.
12. Tukhtarov B.E., Comparative assessment of the biological value of average daily diets in professional athletes of Uzbekistan. Gig. Sanit., 2010, 2, 65-67.